

Exploring the Origin of the COVID-19 Pandemic Using a Non-parametric Approach

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Abstract

The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), has been ongoing for more than three years. However, the origin virus strain responsible for this pandemic remains unclear. To investigate the phylogenetic origin of the COVID-19 pandemic, we utilized a comprehensive SARS-CoV-2 genome dataset and employed a non-parameter approach based on parsimony principle. Following the parsimony principle, we aimed to identify the potential original virus with the fewest total mutations (least mutated strain) within the dataset when compared to all the remaining viral sequences. Our findings indicate that the first identified SARS-CoV-2 virus in Wuhan City, Wuhan-Hu-1 (GenBank accession number: MN908947), is not the least mutated strain. There are three nucleotide differences between Wuhan-Hu-1 and the least mutated strain, namely T2772C, T14143C, and G23138A. In support of this finding, the phylogenetic trees, in conjunction with mutation path analyses, suggest an evolutionary trajectory from the least mutated strain to Wuhan-Hu-1, rather than the reverse. Furthermore, the phylogenetic tree analysis, consisting of 52 major strains, reveals that the least mutated strain occupies the central position. And Jackknife resampling test further supports the conclusion that the least mutated strain acts as the phylogenetic root of all SARS-CoV-2 strains worldwide. Additionally, the least mutated SARS-CoV-2 strain has been designated lineage B.1 according to Pango nomenclature, and all WHO variants of concern can be traced back to lineage B.1. Taken together, these results strongly establish the least mutated SARS-CoV-2 strain as the origin of the COVID-19 pandemic,

rather than Wuhan-Hu-1.

Introduction

December of 2019 is the documented start time of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, which has been ongoing for more than three years with no sign of its ending. This enduring pandemic is initiated by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), which can cause a variety of symptoms in human hosts including fever, cough, fatigue, loss of sense of smell, brain fog, pneumonia, and etc ¹, ². Although it has a lower fatality rate than SARS-CoV, SARS-CoV-2 is remarkably contagious and exhibits cryptic transmission ³⁻⁵. These attributes make SARS-CoV-2 much easier to trigger a global pandemic.

Since the early 2020, throughout the ongoing battle against the COVID-19 pandemic, scientists worldwide have made significant contributions by publishing a multitude of important studies pertaining to the clinical implications of SARS-CoV-2. However, the scientific community remains agnostic about the origin of this pandemic. While the virus was initially discovered in Wuhan City of China, in December of 2019, it doesn't necessarily imply that Wuhan city is its birthplace or that the pandemic originated there ⁶. For instance, HIV virus was first identified in the United States of America during the early 1980s, yet its phylogenetic root extends to West-central Africa ^{7, 8}.

Currently, the researches attempting to unravel the mystery surrounding the origin of SARS-CoV-2 rely on either a fixed reference sequence (e.g., the RaTG13 sequence discovered in Yunnan province of China) or an exceedingly limited dataset (e.g., the

sequencing data solely derived from China) ^{9, 10}. One hypothesis, outlined in a publication in the Science journal, contends that sequencing data contains errors and requires rectification to achieve a desired conclusion ^{10, 11}. To obtain an objective result, we utilized a published non-parameter approach and a comprehensive dataset comprising high-quality SARS-CoV-2 genome data to investigate the origin of the COVID-19 pandemic ^{12, 13}.

Materials and Methods

SARS-CoV-2 genome data collection

SARS-CoV-2 genomes used in this study were obtained from the RCoV19 database ¹⁴, ¹⁵, hosted by National Genomics Data Center (NGDC) in China. RCoV19 incorporates SARS-CoV-2 genome information from GenBank (INSDC dataset) at National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI), EpiCoV™ at Global Initiative on Sharing All Influenza Data (GISAID), GWH/GenBase at NGDC, Novel Coronavirus National Science and Technology Resource Service System at National Genomics Data Center (NMDC) in China, and CNGBdb at China National GeneBank (CNGB). Moreover, it provides de-redundancy processing and cross-references between data sources. Our analysis focused on over 1.4 million non-redundant SARS-CoV-2 genomes worldwide, whose collection dates were between December of 2019 and August of 2021. Due to the updates in the SARS-CoV-2 genome data ¹⁶, we obtained genome sequences and relevant metadata (collection date / location) from source databases at the inception of

this study, instead of relying on RCoV19.

Definition of SARS-CoV-2 strains and quality control

We used the complete coding region identified in MN908947 (first discovered in Wuhan city) as the reference template, to extract the entire coding region from the collected SARS-CoV-2 genome sequences. Each SARS-CoV-2 genome sequence was aligned to the coding region of MN908947 using MUSCLE 3.8.31 with default parameters¹⁷. To ensure data quality, we removed sequences with unknown sites (such as N), retained only the aligned sequence with complete opening reading frame, and excluded sequences with deletion or insertion in its coding region. We also excluded the sequences with more than 200 point mutations compared to our template. Finally, sequences with the same complete coding regions were defined as a single virus strain.

Global point mutation calculation

To identify the least mutated sequence within our dataset, we used a non-parameter approach developed by Shen et al^{12, 13}, to calculate the number of global point mutations in the complete coding regions of SARS-CoV-2. Unlike methods that rely on an outgroup sequence as a reference, this method eliminates the issues arising from inappropriate outgroup selection. Although RaTG13 and SARS-CoV-2 share about 95% similarity in their DNA sequences, they are considered distantly related due to the high sequence identity among SARS-CoV-2s. Using a distantly related sequence as the

outgroup can result in a phenomenon known as long-branch attraction in phylogenetic analysis ¹⁸. This phenomenon causes rapidly evolving sequences to be erroneously placed close to the outgroup, suggesting a closer evolutionary relationship than is accurate. Avoiding this systematic error is crucial for ensuring accurate evolutionary relationships.

Based on the maximum parsimony principle, we used the information within the SARS-CoV-2s' genomes to determine their evolutionary relationship. First, the complete coding regions from different SARS-CoV-2 strains were consolidated into a single alignment. Next, each sequence was compared with all other sequences in this alignment and the cumulative number of point mutations resulting from each comparison was calculated. By pair-wise comparison, we can obtain the number of global point mutations for each sequence.

Mathematical modeling and statistical analysis

The R package (version 4.1.0) was used to perform mathematical modeling and statistical analysis in this study. A *P*-value smaller than 0.05 was viewed as statistically significant.

Phylogenetic analysis and jackknife resampling test

The phylogenetic trees were constructed using neighbor-joining method with gamma

distributed rates in MEGA X ¹⁹. Jackknife resampling test was performed with PHYLIP 3.697 package ²⁰.

Result

Wuhan-Hu-1 (strain-7329) is not the least mutated strain

To identify SARS-CoV-2 strains, we filtered 465,539 high-quality genome sequences from over 1.4 million SARS-CoV-2 genome entries, which were derived from samples collected between December of 2019 and August of 2021 (**Materials and Methods: Definition of SARS-CoV-2 strains and quality control**). These SARS-CoV-2 sequences were grouped into 249,137 SARS-CoV-2 strains based on their sequence identities. The largest SARS-CoV-2 strain comprises 2,930 SARS-CoV-2 sequences, whereas the smallest strain consists of one sequence.

Among the 249,137 SARS-CoV-2 strains, we determined mutations for each strain when compared with the remaining strains, and calculated the number of global point mutations (**Materials and Methods: Global point mutation calculation**). We pinpointed the least mutated strain with the fewest mutations and assigned it the name “strain-1”. According to the maximum parsimony principle, the sequence with the least number of global point mutations represents the ancestral or root sequence from which other sequences in the dataset have evolved.

Our analysis revealed that strain-1 doesn't contain Wuhan-Hu-1, which is referred to as strain-7329 in our study. Specifically, strain-1 consists of 865 SARS-CoV-2 sequences collected between February of 2020 and May of 2021. It covers 50 countries or regions of 10 continents (East Asia, Central Asia, South Asia, Southeast Asia, North America, South America, Central America, Europe, Africa, Oceania) (**Table 1**). Strain-7329 consists of 513 SARS-CoV-2 sequences collected from December of 2019 to July of 2021. As the results indicate, a SARS-CoV-2 strain can exist over a very long period, and the earlier collection time may not necessarily mean earlier emergence.

It is estimated that descendant strain of strain-1 exhibits less point mutations when compared to strain-7329. Upon conducting the sequence alignment analysis for 249,137 SARS-CoV-2 strains, a total of 25,488 variable sites were observed, encompassing 86.67% (25,488/29,409) of the complete coding region of SARS-CoV-2. Assuming strain-1 as the ancestor of all SARS-CoV-2 strains, a total number of 3,860,736 global point mutations were observed in the remaining 249,136 strains using strain-1 as the reference for comparison. On average, each descendant strain exhibits 15.5 point mutations. If strain-7329 were regarded as the ancestor, a total number of 4,564,876 global point mutations were observed. On average, each descendant strain has 18.3 point mutations. Notably, strain-1 and strain-7329 differ by three nucleotides, specifically at the positions 2772, 14143, and 23138 (counting from the first codon).

Early-stage large strains were directly evolved from the least mutated strain (strain-1)

Both strain-1 and strain-7329 represent large strains comprising hundreds of sequences collected across different countries or regions, and they also emerged during the early stage of the pandemic. We identified ten largest early-stage SARS-CoV-2 strains and related genome sequences collected prior to July of 2020, which are strain-1 (865 sequences), strain-10 (2,930 sequences), strain-21 (556 sequences), strain-31 (423 sequences), strain-550 (369 sequences), strain-611 (1,494 sequences), strain-3703 (935 sequences), strain-7329 (513 sequences), strain-37039 (1,240 sequences), and strain-43425 (477 sequences) (**Table 2**). Notably, eight out of these ten strains have already emerged before March of 2020, aligning with the WHO's declaration of COVID-19 as a pandemic on March 11, 2020 (**Figure 1**). By the end of February 2020, strain-1 comprised 27 sequences from nine countries or regions, while strain-7329 consisted of 114 sequences from eight countries or regions (**Figure 1**). It indicates that strain-1 exhibited slightly greater geographic diversity, despite strain-7329 having a larger number of sequences.

Phylogenetic tree analysis showed that the early-stage large strains were directly evolved from strain-1. To analyze the evolutionary relationships among these top ten strains, we reconstructed a phylogenetic tree based on the early-stage sequences. The tree was first rooted using strain-1, and the number of mutations relative to strain-1 was calculated for each strain. Subsequently, the tree was rooted using strain-7329, and the

number of mutations relative to strain-7329 was calculated for each strain. The phylogenetic tree rooted with strain-1 displayed 33 mutations, with all early-stage large strains directly evolving from strain-1 (**Figure 2A**). However, the phylogenetic tree rooted with strain-7329 revealed 51 mutations, and depicted a two-stage early evolution of SARS-CoV-2. In the first stage, strain-7329 gave rise to strain-1 and strain-43425, while in the second stage, the other seven early-stage large strains sprouted from strain-1 (**Figure 2B**).

Related strain analysis suggests extremely low probability for strain-1 evolving from strain-7329

Which strain is more likely to be the ancestor of all SARS-CoV-2s, strain 1 or strain 7329? There are three nucleotide differences between strain-1 and strain-7329. If strain-1 were assumed as the ancestral strain for all SARS-CoV-2s, strain-7329 would have undergone three mutations, namely T2772C, T14143C, and G23138A. Conversely, if strain-7329 were regarded as the starting point, strain-1 would have three mutations C2772T, C14143T, and A23138G. To determine the ancestor strain, we examined the mutation paths associated with these three nucleotide differences.

We identified five intermediate strains between strain-1 and strain-7329: strain-28, strain-29, strain-32, strain-2325, and strain-2326. These intermediate strains share one or two of three mutations mentioned above with strain-1 or strain-7329. If strain-1 were the starting point of the epidemic, we could obtain seven mutations: T2772C for strain-

28, T14143C for strain-29, G23138A for strain-32, T2772C and T14143C for strain-2325, strainT14143C and G23138A for strain-2326. If strain-7239 were the starting point of the epidemic, we could obtain eight mutations: A23138G for strain-2325, C2772T for strain-2326, C14143T and A23138G for strain-28, C2772T and A23138G for strain-29, C2772T and C14143T for strain-32. It is noted that the C14143T mutation in the evolutionary path from strain-7239 to strain-1 appeared simultaneously in strain-28 and strain-32. However, all mutations in the evolutionary path from strain-1 to strain-7239 occurred in a step-wise manner, with each mutation appearing independently. Overall, the step-wise evolution is more probable than a single mutation simultaneously appearing in two strains.

To further examine the mutation paths, we constructed the phylogenetic trees using related strains that share at least one mutation with strain-1 or strain-7329, including strain-4, strain-10, descendant strains of strain-10, as well as the five intermediate strains. If the trees were rooted with strain-1, each point mutation, T2772C or T14143C or G23138A, independently emerged during the evolution towards strain-7329 (**Figures 3A, 3C and 3E**). Conversely, if the trees were rooted with strain-7329, each point mutation, C2772T or C14143T or A23138G, underwent at least two reverse mutations at each site during the evolution towards strain-1 (**Figures 3B, 3D and 3F**). Considering the entire genomic coding region of SARS-CoV-2, which consists of 29,409 nucleotides, the probability of two reverse mutations at one site could be calculated as the square of $(1/29409) \times (1/3)$, resulting in 1.28×10^{-10} . Consequently, the

probability of two reverse mutations occurring at all three sites can be calculated as $(1/29409) \times (1/3)$ raised to the power of 6, yielding 2.12×10^{-30} (the estimated number of stars in our universe is 10^{22}). However, it is noted that SARS-CoV-2 exhibits an extremely low mutation rate, with an accumulation of approximately 1 or 2 mutations per month per strain²¹. Thus, it is highly unlikely that strain-7329 serves as the origin of SARS-CoV-2.

The major strains are evolved from strain-1, not strain-7329

During the evolutionary history of SARS-CoV-2, it is a recurring phenomenon that a dominant strain emerges and spreads widely across different regions of the world, and we call such strains as major strains. We identified 52 major strains in our dataset that each comprises at least 200 sequences. Notably, strain-1 and strain-7329 were also covered. To investigate the evolutionary relationship between strain-1 and the major strains, we performed the phylogenetic analysis. We further added strain-21397 (the Pango name: lineage A) and strain-28468 (proCoV2) in the phylogenetic analysis, which have been suggested as possible origins of SARS-CoV-2^{9, 10}. The unrooted phylogenetic tree incorporating these 54 strains displays an umbrella-like topology (**Figure 4**). Strain-1, assigned Pango lineage B.1, occupies at the center of this unrooted phylogenetic tree. However, strain-21397 (assigned Pango lineage A) and strain-28468 (proCoV2) cluster together on the same branch with strain-7329 (lineage B). As evolution typically begins from a single point, the central position of strain-1 in the tree unequivocally establishes it as the phylogenetic root of the 54 SARS-CoV-2 strains.

The Pango nomenclature names different SARS-CoV-2 strains based on their Spike gene's nucleotide sequences (<https://cov-lineages.org/>)²². **Table 3** provides seven WHO's variants of concern, along with their respective Pango lineage names. The Pango lineage names clearly demonstrate that these variants are all direct descendants of strain-1 (lineage B.1), including the currently prevalent Omicron variant.

Jackknife resampling tests confirm that strain-1 is the phylogenetic root of the COVID-19 pandemic

The up-mentioned phylogenetic analysis using early-stage large strains, related strains, and major strains, all suggest that strain-1 most likely serves as the phylogenetic root of the COVID-19 pandemic. However, these findings don't conclusively establish strain-1 as the ancestor of all SARS-CoV-2 strains. To further investigate this question, we performed jackknife resampling test using the whole dataset with 249,137 strains. The jackknife test was designed as follows. First, we randomly selected 100 strains from our final dataset excluding strain-1 (leave-one-out). Second, we introduced strain-1 to the randomly selected 100 strains, creating a new test. Third, we constructed two neighbor-joining trees based on the new test dataset and the original test dataset, separately. Finally, we examined whether strain-1 was positioned as the phylogenetic root of the new test dataset and whether a clear phylogenetic root was detected in the original test dataset.

By repeating this resampling process 5000 times, we obtained 5000 random neighbor-joining trees with strain-1 and 5000 random neighbor-joining trees without strain-1. This analysis revealed that strain-1 consistently appeared as the phylogenetic root (located at the center of the tree) in all 5000 random neighbor-joining trees where strain-1 was included. In contrast, in all 5000 random neighbor-joining trees without strain-1, no clear phylogenetic root (no central positioned taxon in the tree) was observed. As a result, the jackknife resampling tests provide strong confirmation that strain-1 serves as the phylogenetic root for the entire set of 249,137 SARS-CoV-2 strains, thereby establishing it as the starting point of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Discussion

The debate of the origin of SARS-CoV-2

Are the first SARS-CoV-2 strain infecting human hosts and the SARS-CoV-2 strain responsible for the COVID-19 pandemic the same? Several studies have investigated the origin of SARS-CoV-2 and proposed different perspectives. One study, published in the Science journal, proposes that the COVID-19 pandemic originated from a multiple zoonotic event based on rectified sequencing data from only China ¹⁰. It highlights the need to rectify certain deficiencies in SARS-CoV-2 sequencing data to get a correct result. After rectification, they identified two parallel human SARS-CoV-2 lineages: strain-7329 (lineage B) and strain-21397 (lineage A), which could have originated from a single animal source. According to their study, the presence of both

strain-7329 (lineage B) and strain-21397 (lineage A) as large strains in China during the early stage of the pandemic suggest that the initial transmission of SARS-CoV-2s to humans was likely not caused by a single strain. Another study suggests that the SARS-CoV-2's ancestor was identified after the appearance of strain-7329 (lineage B)⁹. They propose that strain-28468, referred to as proCoV2, is the closest progenitor of SARS-CoV-2. This is because that proCoV2 exhibits a closer relationship to RaTG13, discovered in Yunnan province of China, compared to strain-7329. Notably, there are also three nucleotide differences between proCoV2 and strain-7329⁹.

Our phylogenetic analysis of major SARS-CoV-2 strains demonstrates that both strain-21397 (lineage A) and strain-28468 (proCoV2) share the same evolutionary branch as strain-7329 (lineage B). As a result, they harbor the same point mutations of T2772C, T14143C and G23138A as strain-7329 compared with strain-1 (lineage B.1). The mutation path analysis shows that the strains with these three point mutations are evolved from strain-1. Therefore, neither strain-21397 (lineage A) nor strain-28468 (proCoV2) can be the origin of this pandemic. Both the phylogenetic tree of major SARS-CoV-2 strains and the jackknife resampling tests provide evidence supporting strain-1 as the origin of the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, it is highly likely that strain-1 serves as the ancestor of all SARS-CoV-2 variants capable of infecting humans.

Interestingly, the study that proposes strain-28468 as the progenitor of SARS-CoV-2 also discovered strain-1. They referred to strain-1 as Beta-3 and identified it as a central

point along the SARS-CoV-2 evolutionary path, as depicted in their figure 2⁹. Moreover, their findings indicate that strain-1 is primarily found in the Middle East and North Africa, whereas the documented sequences of strain-1 in public databases are predominantly collected from Europe and North America. Based on their result, strain-1 represents the shortest evolutionary route for the dominant SARS-CoV-2 offshoots. Therefore, it is more reasonable to consider strain-1 as the origin of all SARS-CoV-2 variants, rather than strain-28468 (proCoV2).

About the starting time of the COVID-19 pandemic

We classified 249,137 SARS-CoV-2 strains based on their collection dates, ranging from December of 2019 to August of 2021 (**Table 4**). Using a mathematical model, we analyzed the growth pattern of SARS-CoV-2 strains over time and discovered that it precisely fit a logistic growth model (**Figure 5A**). The mathematical equation for our logistic growth model is as follows: $y = \frac{266700}{1 + e^{(11.3-x)/2.43}}$. This model demonstrates an excellent fit with an R-square value of 0.99. After converted the number of SARS-CoV-2 strains with natural log, we found that the counts of strains collected by December of 2019, January and February of 2020 were fell well below the fitted curve, making them outliers in the mathematical modeling (**Figure 5B**). Specifically, by the end of February 2020, our dataset contained 837 collected SARS-CoV-2 strains, whereas the logistic growth model predicted that this number should have been 5,659. This indicates that the COVID-19 pandemic likely started earlier than December of 2019, with multiple SARS-CoV-2 strains spreading cryptically across

many parts of the world before the first report case in Wuhan City, China.

Given that the pandemic didn't originate in December of 2019, it becomes important to determine its actual start date. With three nucleotide differences between strain-1 and strain-7329, and considering the estimated mutation rate of SARS-CoV-2 to be 1 or 2 mutations per month, the molecular clock suggests that strain-1 might have emerged as early as July or August of 2019. This estimation is based on the assumption that the transmission of Wuhan SARS-CoV-2 began in November of 2019^{21, 23}.

According to the equation for our logistic growth model, $y = \frac{266700}{1 + e^{(11.3-x)/2.43}}$, $y = 1.54$ (the number of strains) when $x = -18$ (months). This result indicates that $x = -18$ is June of 2018 on the time line when $x = 0$ is December of 2019, we would have 1 or 2 of SARS-CoV-2 strains in June of 2018 ($y = 1$ or 2). Thus, the mathematical model predicts that the first SARS-CoV-2 may have emerged as early as June of 2018.

There appears to be a notable discrepancy between the molecular clock estimation and the mathematical model prediction regarding the origin time of SARS-CoV-2. Analysis of sewage samples collected in Spain indicates a possible presence of SARS-CoV-2 as early as March of 2019²⁴, which precedes the molecular clock estimation. This suggests the potential existence of SARS-CoV-2 even before 2019, and raises the possibility of another round of SARS-CoV-2 transmission occurring between June of 2018 and July

of 2019 in unknown animal hosts. Based on the sewage sample analysis and the mathematical model prediction, strain-1 might be the product of this round of transmission.

Why the COVID-19 pandemic had not been detected in the first place?

Given a number of infected individuals have mild or no symptom at all ²⁵, the SARS-CoV-2 transmission pattern is very cryptic. This, in turn, increases the difficulty of its detection in human population in the first place. Furthermore, as the virus likely emerged in the late summer of 2019 in the Northern Hemisphere, respiratory infection symptoms tend to be attenuated and the infected patients would have a better prognosis in warm temperatures. These features may have led to the virus being overlooked during its initial small-scale outbreaks.

The first reported strain-7329 in Wuhan City differs from strain-1 in the coding region site of 23138. Specifically, strain-1 has a guanine (G) while strain-7329 has an adenine (A), which leads to the change of 614th amino acid in their Spike protein. Strain-1 has a glycine (codon GGT, G614) at this amino acid site while strain-7329 has an aspartic acid (codon GAT, D614). One study shows that the SARS-CoV-2 with G614 Spike protein is more contagious than the one with D614, because G614 is associated with the higher upper respiratory tract viral loads ²⁶. It implies that the SARS-CoV-2 with G614 tends to cause cold-like symptoms since it targets the upper respiratory tract, whereas the SARS-CoV-2 with D614 is more likely to infect the lower respiratory tract

and causes bronchitis or pneumonia, both of which have much worse symptoms than cold. The more severe symptoms of D614 explains why Wuhan first detected the COVID-19 virus.

When we analyzed the meta data, we found that many countries submitted their data to public databases without providing the corresponding virus collection dates, especially the sequences in ten largest SARS-CoV-2 strains before July of 2020. This behavior created a great difficulty for the early warning and source tracing of the pandemic.

Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic originated from strain-1 (lineage B.1) and started in July or August of 2019. So far, all discovered SARS-CoV-2s are its direct descendants. The spread of strain-1 itself is a super transmission event which covered five continents and lasted almost 18 months.

Data availability

The data and results of this study can be downloaded from <https://github.com/libing-shen/Least-mutated-sequence/tree/main/hcov2>.

Compliance and ethics

All authors declare no potential competing interest. This work used the online data and ethical approval is not applicable.

Authors' contributions

LBS collected and analyzed the data. LBS wrote and revised the manuscript.

Consent for publication

The author consented the right for publication.

Competing interests

The author declares no potential competing interest.

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Figures and tables

Figure 1. The geographic distribution of eight large SARS-CoV-2 strains by the end of February 2020. The number behind each country or region indicates the number of strain sequences collected there.

Figure 2. The phylogenetic analysis of ten largest SARS-CoV-2 strains. **A.** The neighbor-join tree of ten largest SARS-CoV-2 strains rooted with strain-1. The number before each taxon indicates its nucleotide differences compared with strain-1. **B.** The neighbor-join tree of ten largest SARS-CoV-2 strains rooted with strain-7329. The number before each taxon indicates its nucleotide differences compared with strain-7329.

Figure 3. The phylogenetic analyses of nine SARS-CoV-2 strains for the mutation path of nucleotide sites of 2772, 14143, and 23138. **A.** The neighbor-join tree rooted with strain-1 for the mutation path of nucleotide site of 2772. The **light blue branch** indicates T2772C mutation. **B.** The neighbor-join tree rooted with strain-7329 for the mutation path of nucleotide site of 2772. The black branch indicates C2772T mutation and the **light blue branch** indicates T2772C mutation. **C.** The neighbor-join tree rooted with strain-1 for the mutation path of nucleotide site of 14143. The **light green branch** indicates T14143C mutation. **D.** The neighbor-join tree rooted with strain-7329 for the mutation path of nucleotide site of 14143. The black branch indicates C14143T mutation and the **light green branch** indicates T14143C mutation. **E.** The neighbor-join tree rooted with strain-1 for the mutation path of nucleotide site of 23138. The **magenta**

branch indicates G23128A mutation. F. The neighbor-join tree rooted with strain-7329 for the mutation path of nucleotide site of 23138. The black branch indicates A23128G mutation and the magenta branch indicates G23128A mutation.

Figure 4. The phylogenetic analysis of 52 major SARS-CoV-2 strains plus the lineage A strain and the proCoV2 strain proposed Kumar et al. The red filled cycle ● indicates strain-1 (lineage B.1). The green filled cycle ● indicate strain-7329 (lineage B). The light blue filled cycle ● indicates strain-28468 (proCoV2). The dark filled cycle ● indicates strain-21397 (lineage A).

Figure 5. The logistic growth model for SARS-CoV-2's strains. **A.** The logistic growth curve of the number of SARS-CoV-2's strains. **B.** The logistic growth curve of the natural logarithm of the number of SARS-CoV-2's strains. The filled triangle ▲ indicates the outlier of the model.

Table 1. The geographic distribution of strain-1 sequences.

Continent	Country or Region	Total
East Asia	Hong Kong (10), Japan (7)	17
Central Asia	Saudi Arabia (3), Israel (2), United Arab Emirates (1)	6
South Asia	India (32), Bangladesh (1)	33
Southeast Asia	Singapore (3), Malaysia (2)	5
North America	United States (215), Canada (71),	286
South America	Brazil (13), Chile (3)	16
Central America	Saint Martin (5), Guatemala (1)	6
Europe	United Kingdom (98), Italy (75), Germany (69), France (34), Finland (26), Iceland (24), Switzerland (21), Belgium (15), Sweden (13), Austria (12), Norway (7), Czech Republic (7), Netherlands (7), Luxembourg (6), Bosnia and Herzegovina (6), Russia (4), Turkey (4), Estonia (3), Denmark (3), Moldova (3), Spain (3), Ireland (2), Portugal (2), Greece (2), Serbia (2), Poland (2), Georgia (2), Lithuania (1)	453
Africa	South Africa (15), Uganda (4), Kenya (4), Tunisia (2), Morocco (1)	26
Oceania	Australia (13), New Zealand (4)	17

Table 2. The ten largest SARS-CoV-2 strains by the end of July 2020 and their total numbers of sequences month by month.

Strain name	Num of total collected sequences	Num of sequences by 2020/02/29	Num of sequences by 2020/03/31	Num of sequences by 2020/04/30	Num of sequences by 2020/05/31	Num of sequences by 2020/06/30	Num of sequences by 2020/07/31
strain -1	865	26	578	760	786	796	810
strain -10	2930	7	2114	2703	2786	2810	2822
strain -21	556	9	382	530	544	548	549
strain -31	423	0	334	406	410	410	410
strain -550	369	4	222	345	348	351	357
strain -611	1494	11	798	1189	1319	1387	1415

strain -3703	935	3	235	889	917	919	920
strain -7329	513	134	293	318	346	351	355
strain - 3703 9	1240	0	0	0	4	106	1038
strain - 4342 5	477	8	412	456	458	470	470

Table 3. The WHO name and Pango lineage information for SARS-CoV-2 variants of concern.

WHO label	Pango lineage	First Detected	Number of reported countries
Alpha	B.1.1.7	United Kingdom	190
Beta	B.1.351	South Africa	140
Delta	B.1.617.2	India	170
Gamma	B.1.1.28.1	Brazil	90
Lambda	B.1.1.1.1	Peru	30
Mu	B.1.621	Colombia	57
Omicron	B.1.1.529	Botswana	The current global variant

Table 4. The total number of collected SARS-CoV-2 sequences and strains from December of 2019 to August of 2021.

Date	Number of sequences	Number of strains	Strain-to-sequence ratio
2019/12/31	44	13	0.295
2020/1/31	687	314	0.457
2020/02/29	1817	837	0.461
2020/03/31	28407	11706	0.412
2020/04/30	52089	23186	0.445
2020/05/31	65743	30816	0.468
2020/06/30	80933	39079	0.483
2020/07/31	102654	49496	0.482
2020/08/31	121370	58396	0.481
2020/09/30	143970	69102	0.48
2020/10/31	178069	85788	0.482
2020/11/30	221474	108945	0.492

2020/12/31	277588	139522	0.503
2021/01/31	348961	182621	0.523
2021/02/28	400952	214350	0.535
2021/03/31	436513	235393	0.539
2021/04/30	449894	243337	0.541
2021/05/31	454206	245922	0.541
2021/06/30	455730	247084	0.542
2021/07/31	457179	247577	0.542
2021/08/31	462456	247587	0.535

Note: 3083 SARS-CoV-2 sequences and 1550 SARS-CoV-2 strains in our dataset have no documented collection date.